

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable 8.2

**1st EJP SOIL EU Policymaker Forum – policy
needs workshop**

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Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	4
List of Figures.....	4
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	4
1. Introduction.....	5
2. EJP SOIL EU Policymaker workshop event details.....	6
2.1 EU Policymaker workshop programme and invite information.....	6
2.2 List of invited participants to the EU Policymaker workshop	8
2.3 Policy stakeholders that participated in to the EU Policymaker workshop.....	9
2.4 Reporting of results of the EU Policymaker workshop	9

List of Tables

Table 1. EJP SOIL EU Policymaker Workshop programme

Table 2. List of invited stakeholders and stakeholder organisations to the workshop

Table 3. List of policy stakeholders that participated in the workshop

List of acronyms and abbreviations

EJP SOIL: European Joint Programme for Soil

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

WP: Work Package

1. Introduction

Agricultural soil management in the EU is impacted by a diversity of binding and non-binding agri-environmental policies. EJP SOIL work package (WP) 8 aims to support a strengthened science-policy interface in the area of agricultural soil management and climate change mitigation and adaptation. The focus is to provide support for the implementation of soil C accounting, the delivery of soil ecosystem services and enhanced soil quality and optimised soil management and fertilisation practices. Some of the key objectives are to:

- Identify and address current and future policy needs (e.g. CAP, Climate Policy, Land Degradation Neutrality) for new knowledge and scientific evidence base at a range of scales as appropriate (i.e. regional, national and European);
- Facilitate access to scientific knowledge at appropriate scales for national and European policy makers and support the effective use of scientific results for policy design at these different scales;
- Provide scientific support to policymakers to enable the design of effective policy measures at different scales, especially in relation to soil carbon accounting;

The approach taken in WP8 is to provide evidence-based recommendations to EU and national/regional policymakers on optimal agricultural soil management through:

- a. Establishing open dialogue and information flow between the EJP consortium and relevant EU and national/regional policymakers with governance over agriculture, environment and climate policy;
- b. Seeking information from policymakers in order to facilitate access to, and more fully exploit scientific results that are already available for informing, developing and implementing soil related policy.

EJP SOIL Task 8.2 Understand & Analyse

The focus of EJP SOIL T8.2 - Understand & Analyse, is to gain an understanding of policymaker needs for research and soil quality indicator monitoring information, especially in the area of soil C accounting and soil ecosystem services. In this task The EJP SOIL seeks to identify and address current and future policymakers needs to address current and future policy needs (e.g. Common Agricultural Policy, Land Degradation Neutrality) for new knowledge and scientific evidence base at a range of scales as appropriate (e.g. national, regional, European). These needs will be identified through supporting dialogue with policymakers at national and EU levels. In this report, we provide summary information and details of the 1st EJP SOIL EU Policymaker workshop event that was held on the 28th January 2021 (Deliverable 8.2)

2. EJP SOIL – EU Policymaker workshop event details

2.1. EU Policymaker workshop programme and invite information

In November 2020 a “save the date” invite was sent to the list of EU policy stakeholders (Table 2) indicating that the event would be held on 28th January 2021. The details of the invite and workshop programme are as follows;

EJP SOIL – EU Policymaker workshop

Strengthening the science to policy interface – meeting policy needs now and in future

½ Day Workshop: Thursday 28th January starting at 9.00 CET

Venue: ON-LINE Workshop

Website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Europe has committed to improving the management of agricultural soils to achieve ambitious goals on reducing greenhouse gases, environmental pressures and land degradation from agriculture and food production while enhancing multiple ecosystem services such as biodiversity and water purification etc. Critical policy decisions on climate smart and sustainable soil management will be needed to reach these goals and increased science based policy advice will be in high demand, but may vary across the different climatic regions of Europe and according to agricultural practices. The aim of this EU Policymaker Workshop is strengthening evidence based policy formulation across Europe. This workshop will facilitate a conversation on policymaker needs and the exchange of experiences, challenges ideas and best practices on science to policy interaction.

The European Joint Programme for Soils (EJP SOIL) aims to enhance the contribution of agricultural soils to key societal challenges including climate change adaptation and mitigation, sustainable agricultural production, ecosystem services provision and prevention and restoration of land and soil degradation. Join us in an interactive half-day EU Policymaker workshop where you inform us of your key needs to reach ambitions from the policy perspective.

The workshop will address policy realisations and needs under the current policy framework, as well as needs to realise emerging policies and have your say in our final session on future horizon scanning of policies towards 2050.

Table 1. EJP SOIL EU Policymaker Workshop programme

Workshop Programme		
Time	Session details	
9.00	Participants join workshop web-link, Workshop description and programme	David Wall
9.10	Welcome & opening address by Claire Chenu <i>(Coordinator of EJP SOIL, INRAe)</i>	Claire Chenu
9.25	<p>Session 1: “Identifying current policy ambitions and future soil aspirational goals”</p> <p><i>Goal: to identify the soil aspirational goals at the EU level and related policy needs, by addressing three questions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>How wide is the gap between EU policy targets and realisations?</i> - <i>Are the current EU policy targets futureproof with a horizon to 2050?</i> - <i>Which soil challenges should be prioritized in the EU?</i> <p><i>Co-led by EV-ILVO and WUR</i></p>	<p>Miro Jacob,</p> <p>Greet Ruyschaert,</p> <p>Peter Maenhout</p>
	<p>Session introduction (5min) <i>Group sessions with input and expert opinion from policymaker participants</i></p> <p>Policy realisation and aspirational goals (40 min)</p> <p>Policy prioritization (30 min)</p> <p>Session 1: final discussion and conclusions (15 min) <i>Rapporteurs in each group will take notes of specific policies discussed, targets to be reviewed and soil challenges that should be prioritized.</i></p>	
11.00	Coffee break (15 mins)	
11.15	<p>Session 2: “Aligning EJP SOIL research with EU Policy Stakeholder needs and requirements for emerging and future soil policy”</p> <p><i>Goal: to identify emerging and future soil policy needs and requirements by addressing these questions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What knowledge, implementation, monitoring and reporting needs are required for emerging soil related policy?</i> - <i>What new policy options & innovations could support climate smart and sustainable soil management in future?</i> <p><i>Co-led by CREA & Teagasc</i></p>	<p>David Wall,</p> <p>Lilian O’Sullivan,</p> <p>Guido Bonati</p>
	<p>Session introduction (5 min) <i>Group sessions with input and expert opinion from policymaker participants</i></p> <p>Needs for emerging agricultural soil policy (CAP, EU Green Deal etc.)(35 min)</p> <p>Horizon scanning activity – future soil related policy needs & ideas (35 min)</p> <p>Session 2: final discussion and conclusions (15 min) <i>Rapporteurs in each group will take notes specific of policy needs, scientific gaps and information requirements, and ideas for future soil policy, for evaluating and monitoring policy and new initiatives & incentives for supporting soil policy.</i></p>	
12.45	Workshop Close	David Wall

2.2. List of invited participants to the EU Policymaker workshop

The invite list of EU policy stakeholders (Table 2) was developed and selected following consultation with policy contacts at the European Commission (EC), and other EU and high-level organisations that interact with soil policy, and by talking with EJP SOIL partners who had been involved in previous stakeholder workshops. From this list of policy stakeholders our aim was to generate interest and representation from the main agricultural soil policy stakeholder at EU level including the EC Director General units of CLIMA, AGRI, ENV & R&I -RTD, and EU policy organisations as well as farmer and landowner representative groups who are involved in shaping soil policy in Europe.

Table 2. List of invited stakeholders and stakeholder organisations to the workshop

	SURNAME	FIRST NAME	ORGANISATION
1	Kay	Simon	EC DG CLIMA
2	Mueller	Christine	EC DG CLIMA
3	Forlin	Valeria	EC DG CLIMA
4	Holzleitner	Christian	EC DG CLIMA
5	Schneegans	Annette	EC DG AGRI
6	Iglesias	Marta	EC DG AGRI
7	Rosenow	Kerstin	EC DG AGRI
8	Maeder	Stephanie	EC DG AGRI
9	Campos Rodrigu	Isirido	EC DG AGRI
10	Ranner	Herwig	EC DG AGRI
11	Di Virgilio	Nocola	EC DG AGRI
12	Barbero	Micro	EC DG ENV
13	Vettori	Andrea	EC DG ENV
14	Wejchert	Jakub	EC DG ENV
15	Torre	Jean-Paul	EC DG ENV
16	Kovacevic	Vujadin	EC DG ENV
17	Roche	Leanne	EC DG ENV
18	Masson	Josiane	EC DG ENV
19	Svetlana	Chovancova	EC DG ENV
18	Kommer	Judit	EC DG Research and Innovation RTD
19	Wehrheim	Peter	EC DG Research and Innovation RTD
20	Andrade	Onelica	EC DG Research and Innovation RTD
21	Baritz	Rainer	European Environment Agency
22	Fussel	Hans-Martin	European Environment Agency
23	Pinto-Correia	Teresa	Soil Mission Board
27	Manderscheid	Petra	FACCI-JPI
28	Jones	Arwyn	EC JRC
29	Barreiro Hurle	Jesus	EC JRC
30	Van Liedekerke	Marc	EC JRC
31	Montanarella	Luca	EC JRC
32	de Ruiter	Peter	ITPS
33	Caon	Lucrezia	
34	Vargas	Ronald	FAO
35	Le Foll	Stéphane	"4 per 1000"
36	Lukáčová	Zuzana	MILIEU LTD, Law and Policy Consulting
37	McNeil	Alicia	MILIEU LTD, Law and Policy Consulting
38	Muro	Melanie	MILIEU LTD, Law and Policy Consulting
39	Komlos	Daniel	Copa and Cogeca
40	Peric	Nenad	Copa and Cogeca
41	Neagu	Oana	Copa and Cogeca
42	Pesonen	Pekka	Copa and Cogeca
43	Miles	Branwen	Copa and Cogeca
44	Picot	Marion	CEJA
45	Debernardini	Mariana	CEJA
46	Scriban	Alain	European Landowners' Organization (ELO)
47	Curley	Niall	European Landowners' Organization (ELO)
48	Mausser	Harold	European Forest Institute (EFI)
49	van der Bosch	Rik	ISRIC
50	Ittner	Sophie	Ecologic
51	Frelih-larsen	Ana	Ecologic
52	Herb	Irina	Ecologic
53	Ralph	Bodle	Ecologic

2.3. Policy stakeholders who participated in the EU Policymaker workshop

Following communication with each of the policy stakeholders in January 2021 the participants registered for the EU Policymaker workshop using the event registration link developed by EJP SOIL. This list of EU policy stakeholders that participated is shown in table 3.

Table 3. List of policy stakeholders that participated in the workshop

Registered Participant List EJP SOIL EU Policymaker Workshop			
	Firstname	Surname	Organization
1	Yusuf	Yigini	Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN
2	Suzie	Lukacova	Milieu
3	Rainer	Baritz	European Environment Agency
4	Petra	Manderscheid	JPI Climate
5	Niall	Curley	European Landowners' Organization (ELO)
6	Nenad	Peric	COPA-COGECA
7	Maria Jose	Amaral	European Commission / REA
8	Leanne	Roche	European Commission
9	Kerstin	Rosenow	European Commission
10	Christine	Mueller	EC
11	Annette	Schneegans	European Commission
12	Annabelle	Williams	RISE Foundation
13	Alina	Syp	Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation
14	Svetlana	Chovancova	EC DG Environment
15	Ronald	Vargas	FAO
16	Ralph	Bodle	Ecologic Institute
17	Pilar	Vizcaino	REA-EC
18	Peter	De Ruyter	University of Amsterdam
19	Nicola	Di Virgilio	EC DG Agriculture and Rural Development
20	Mariana	Debernardini	CEJA
21	Luca	Montanarella	European Commission
22	Hinke	De Groot	Permanent Representation of the Netherlands to the EU
23	Arwyn	Jones	European Commission Joint Research Centre
24	Delphine	Dupeux	European Landowners' Organization (ELO)
25	Anna	Luise	UNCCD - CST
26	Mustafa Abdulla	Yurtoglu	UNCCD
27	Paul	Luu	4 per 1000

2.4. Reporting of results of the EU Policymaker workshop

During the workshop an number of questions were posed during the session 1 and session 2. Notes and written responses we collected by the EJP SOIL team during the stakeholder dialogue and this information and a list of stakeholder needs will be developed into a Policy Stakeholder Needs Report.

